

Online Advertising Network System

A project paper submitted in fulfillment of the requirements for the Degree of Bachelor of Science (Honors) in Computer Science and Engineering

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Declaration

We, Abu Sayed, Joynob Akter, and Ashik Shadnan Hossain, declare that this system titled **ONLINE ADVERTISING NETWORK SYSTEM**, and the work presented in it are our own.

We confirm that:

- This work has been done wholly or mainly while in candidature for a B.Sc degree in Computer Science and Engineering at National University.
- Where any part of this dissertation has previously been submitted for a degree or any other qualification at National University or any other institution, this has been clearly stated.
- Where we have consulted the published work of others, this is always clearly attributed.
- Where we have quoted from the work of others, the source is always given. With the exception of such quotations, this dissertation is entirely our own work.
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Certificate

I do hereby declare that the research works embodied in this project entitled **ONLINE ADVERTISING NETWORK SYSTEM** is the outcome of an original work carried out by Abu Sayed, Joynob Akter, and Ashik Shadhan Hossain under my direct supervision.

I further certify that the dissertation meets the requirements and the standard for the degree of B.Sc (Honours) in Computer Science and Engineering.

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Abstract

In today's digital age, online advertising is a major source of revenue for businesses of all sizes. However, the current system of online advertising is inefficient and wasteful. Publishers and advertisers often have difficulty finding each other, and consumers are bombarded with irrelevant ads.

This project proposes a new online advertising network system that will address these inefficiencies and improve the overall experience for everyone involved. The system will use a combination of machine learning and artificial intelligence to match publishers and advertisers, and to deliver relevant ads to consumers. The system will also be designed to protect user privacy and to ensure that ads are displayed in a way that is not disruptive to the user experience.

The proposed system has the potential to revolutionize the online advertising industry. By making the system more efficient and effective, it will generate more revenue for publishers and advertisers, and it will provide a better experience for consumers.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1. Introduction

Imagine a world where people use computers and phones to show others things they want to sell or tell about. This is what we call advertising, and it's like when you see colorful pictures and messages on your tablet or computer screen.

Now, a clever team of friends – Sayed, Joynob, and Ashik – have come together to make advertising on the computer even better and easier. We call our special project the **Online Advertising Network System**, or **OANS** for short.

In today's digital age, where our world is interconnected through screens and clicks, advertising has transformed into a vital component of business strategies. This is a platform that not only simplifies online advertising but also maximizes savings and local market advantages.

Project Essence and Local Impact

The heart of the OANS project beats with the idea of supporting local enterprises in a global digital marketplace. We have united our efforts to develop a unique solution that tailors online advertising to our local market's needs and characteristics. This project isn't just about technology; it's about empowering local businesses, reducing foreign currency dependencies, and enhancing economic growth right here at home.

A User-Friendly Approach

Understanding the intricacies of technology might seem overwhelming, but the OANS project takes a user-friendly path. We have chosen a set of tools that are easy to understand and navigate. The project uses familiar building blocks like PHP, JavaScript, HTML, CSS, and the CodeIgniter framework. This approach ensures that even those who aren't tech-savvy can benefit from the OANS platform without feeling lost in a sea of technical jargon.

A Local Economy Booster

What sets OANS apart is its focus on the local economy. Our platform operates in our own currency and caters to the unique challenges and opportunities of our local market. This means businesses can avoid unnecessary foreign currency exchange costs, save on extra taxes, and capitalize on their local identity.

Project Goals and Achievements

We have carefully crafted the OANS project to be a catalyst for change. By fostering local business growth and reducing reliance on foreign resources, OANS envisions a future where our local economy thrives through sustainable and strategic online

advertising. This is more than just a project; it's a stepping stone towards an empowered local business ecosystem.

As we journey deeper into the OANS project, we invite you to discover not only its technical prowess but also its potential to shape our local market landscape. Our endeavor isn't solely about code; it's about bolstering our community's economic foundation and empowering our businesses to thrive in the digital era.

1.1. Background Study

Online advertising has become an integral part of the digital world as businesses aim to reach their target audience through the internet. With the rise of e-commerce and online services, the demand for an efficient and effective online advertising network system has grown. The system provides a platform for advertisers and publishers to connect and engage with their audience in a more targeted and personalized manner.

The advertising industry has undergone significant changes in recent years, with a shift towards online advertising. According to a report by eMarketer, global digital ad spending is expected to reach \$455 billion by 2024. This growth is fueled by the increasing use of mobile devices and social media platforms.

The proposed online advertising network system aims to provide a user-friendly and reliable platform for advertisers and publishers to manage their campaigns and monetize their websites or apps. The system will be developed using PHP language and will have three types of access: one for the admin, one for advertisers, and one for webmasters/publishers.

The system will allow advertisers to create and manage their advertising campaigns, including targeting options such as geographic, demographic, and behavioral targeting. Publishers will be able to monetize their websites or apps by displaying ads and tracking their performance through comprehensive reporting and analytics.

The system will offer a centralized platform for advertisers and publishers to connect, making the process of buying and selling online advertising space more efficient and effective. It will reduce the need for traditional methods of advertising and verification, and provide an automated incremental ad impression count to help reduce the time taken for result publishing.

Hardware: In the development phase, only a computer will be required. In the production phase, additional hardware such as servers will be needed to host the web app.

Software: The system will be developed using PHP language, and the front-end and back-end coding will be done using VS Code. Associative databases such as MySQL will be used to keep track of CRUD operations in the database.

This documentation starts with a formal introduction to the proposed online advertising network system. After the introduction, the analysis and design of the project will be described, including requirement analysis, ERD, and input-output design. The documentation will also include a design and table diagram. Finally, the documentation will be completed with a conclusion section.

The system will be developed in PHP language with the help of Laravel Framework, Mysql and will have three types of access:

1. **Admin:** The admin will have the ability to create and manage publishers, advertisers, and campaigns.
2. **Advertiser:** The advertiser will be able to create and manage campaigns, and to track the performance of their campaigns.
3. **Publisher:** The publisher/webmaster will be able to create and manage ad spaces, and to receive payments from advertisers.

The system will be hosted on a cloud server and will be accessible to users from anywhere in the world.

This project is being developed by Abu Sayed, Joynob Akter, and Ashik Shadnan Hossain. We are all students at the Bangladesh Institute of Science and Technology (BIST). We are excited to be working on this project and we believe that it has the potential to make a real difference in the online advertising industry.

1.2. Objective

The objective of the Online Advertising Network System varies depending on the type of user:

Admin

The objective of the admin is to manage and monitor the overall system. This includes managing user accounts, ensuring compliance with advertising policies, and monitoring system performance. The admin also has the ability to create and manage campaigns on behalf of advertisers.

- Create and manage publishers, advertisers, and campaigns.
- Monitor the performance of the system and make necessary adjustments.
- Resolve any issues that may arise.

Advertiser

The objective of the advertiser is to create and manage advertising campaigns to promote their products or services. This includes defining target audiences, creating ad creatives, and setting budgets. Advertisers also have access to reporting and analytics to track the performance of their campaigns.

- Create and manage campaigns.
- Track the performance of their campaigns.
- Target their ads to specific audiences.
- Pay for their ads.

Webmaster/Publisher

The objective of the webmaster/publisher is to monetize their website or app by displaying ads from advertisers. This includes setting up ad spaces, defining ad formats, and managing ad placements. Publishers also have access to reporting and analytics to track the performance of their ad placements.

- Create and manage ad spaces.
- Receive payments from advertisers.
- Track the performance of their ad spaces.
- Monitor the quality of the ads that are displayed on their websites.

Overall, the objective of the online advertising network system is to provide a platform for advertisers and publishers to connect and engage with their target audiences in a more targeted and personalized manner. The system aims to reduce the need for traditional methods of advertising and verification and provide a more efficient and effective way of buying and selling online advertising space.

1.3. Motivation

The motivation behind creating an online advertising network system is to provide a more efficient and effective way for advertisers and publishers to connect and engage with their target audiences. Traditional methods of advertising, such as print and television, can be expensive and not always targeted to the right audience. With

an online advertising network system, advertisers can reach their target audience more easily and at a lower cost.

In addition, the system provides a way for publishers to monetize their website or app by displaying ads from advertisers. This allows them to generate revenue and continue producing quality content for their audience.

The system also aims to provide a more secure and transparent way of buying and selling online advertising space. By using a centralized platform, the system can ensure compliance with advertising policies and provide transparency in reporting and analytics. This reduces the risk of fraud and ensures that advertisers are getting the value they pay for.

Another motivation behind creating an online advertising network system could be to reduce dependency on foreign currencies like the US dollar and encourage the use of the local currency, such as the Bangladeshi taka. This can help to reduce the cost of advertising for local businesses, who would otherwise have to pay for advertising in foreign currencies, which can be expensive due to exchange rate fluctuations.

By using the local currency, the online advertising network system can provide a more affordable and accessible platform for local businesses to advertise their products or services. This can help to boost the local economy and support small businesses, which are often the backbone of local communities.

Moreover, using the local currency can also help to reduce the risk of currency fluctuations and instability in the global financial market. This can provide a more stable and reliable platform for advertisers and publishers to conduct their business without worrying about the impact of global economic trends on their advertising budgets.

Reducing the dependency on foreign currencies and encouraging the use of the local currency can be another motivation for creating an online advertising network system, which can provide a more affordable, accessible, and stable platform for local businesses to advertise their products or services.

Overall, the motivation behind creating an online advertising network system is to provide a more efficient, effective, and secure way for advertisers and publishers to engage with their target audience and monetize their content.

1.4. Expected Outcome

The expected outcome of creating an online advertising network system is to provide a centralized platform for advertisers and publishers to connect and engage with

their target audience in a more efficient and effective way. The system should be able to provide the following outcomes:

1. **Increased efficiency:** The system should allow advertisers to easily create and manage their advertising campaigns, and publishers to easily monetize their website or app. This can reduce the time and effort required to conduct advertising business.
2. **Better targeting:** The system should allow advertisers to target their audience more accurately based on demographics, interests, behavior, and other relevant factors. This can help to improve the effectiveness of advertising and reduce wastage of ad spend.
3. **Improved reporting and analytics:** The system should provide transparent and accurate reporting and analytics, including metrics such as click-through rates, conversion rates, and return on investment (ROI). This can help advertisers and publishers to optimize their campaigns and improve their results over time.
4. **Enhanced security:** The system should provide a secure platform for buying and selling online advertising space, including compliance with advertising policies and regulations. This can help to reduce the risk of fraud and ensure that advertisers are getting the value they pay for.
5. **Reduced cost:** The system should provide a more affordable platform for advertisers and publishers to conduct their business, by reducing the cost of advertising and providing more opportunities for monetization. This can help to support local businesses and boost the local economy.
6. **Reduced dependency on the US dollar:** Our system will allow advertisers and publishers to use their local currency, which will save them time and money.
7. **Enhanced targeting:** The system's ability to target specific countries, operating systems, browsers, device types, and categories can help advertisers to more effectively reach their desired audience and improve their ad performance.
8. **Protection against click-fraud:** The system's click-fraud protection can help to prevent fraudulent clicks and impressions, ensuring that advertisers are getting accurate and valid data on their ad performance.

9. **Multiple payment models:** The system's ability to support both CPC and CPM payment models can provide flexibility for advertisers and help to improve the return on investment for their advertising spend.
10. **User and campaign management:** The system's ability to manage users, sites, campaigns, and ads can provide a streamlined experience for advertisers and publishers, allowing them to easily create and manage their advertising efforts.
11. **Detailed statistics:** The system's ability to track impressions and clicks can provide detailed analytics and insights into the performance of advertising campaigns, allowing advertisers and publishers to optimize their efforts and improve their results.
12. **Secure access:** The system's ability to provide separate admin, advertiser/webmaster, and moderator accounts can help to ensure that each user has access only to the features and data that they need, improving security and data privacy.
13. **Compatibility with popular browsers:** The system's compatibility with popular web browsers such as IE11, Firefox, Safari, Opera, Chrome, and Edge can ensure that advertisers and publishers can access the platform from a wide range of devices and operating systems.

Chapter 2

Feasibility Study

2. Feasibility Study

The purpose of this feasibility study is to assess the technical, economic, and legal feasibility of developing an Online Advertising Network System (OANS). The OANS will be a platform that allows advertisers to place their ads on websites and mobile apps. The system will track the number of impressions and clicks on each ad, and advertisers will be charged based on these metrics.

2.1. Technical feasibility

The technical feasibility of the OANS has been assessed and found to be feasible. The team has the necessary skills and experience to develop the system, and the necessary resources are available. The system will be developed using PHP, JavaScript, HTML, CSS, MySQL and CodeIgniter software framework. PHP, a popular programming language that is well-suited for developing web applications, MySQL is a popular database management system and CodeIgniter is a powerful PHP framework with a very small footprint, built for developers.

2.2. Economic Feasibility

The economic feasibility of the OANS has also been assessed and found to be feasible. The system is expected to generate enough revenue to cover its costs and generate a profit. The system will generate revenue from two sources:

1. **Advertising fees:** Advertisers will pay to place their ads on the system. The amount of the fee will be based on the number of impressions and clicks on each ad. In addition to the advertising fee, there will be a transaction fee also.
2. **Withdrawal fees:** Publishers will be charged withdrawal fees when they withdraw money from their account.
3. **Payment fees:** Advertisers will be charged a payment fee when they add money to their account or pay for a campaign.

2.3. Organizational feasibility

The system is compatible with the organization's existing systems and processes. The organization is willing to change its processes and procedures to accommodate the system.

2.4. Market feasibility

Market feasibility refers to the analysis of whether the proposed Online Advertising Network System (OANS) is a viable solution in the current market. To determine market feasibility, several factors need to be considered, including competition, target market, and demand.

Competition: The online advertising market is highly competitive, with numerous established players such as Google AdSense, Facebook Ads, and Amazon Advertising. However, the OANS offers unique features such as click-fraud protection, visual ad unit builder, and internal user support system that may differentiate it from the competitors.

Target Market: The target market for the OANS includes businesses and website owners who want to advertise their products or services online. The system's ability to target specific countries, OS, browsers, device types, and categories may attract customers who want to reach a particular audience.

Demand: The demand for online advertising is continuously increasing, and the global online advertising market is expected to reach \$389 billion by 2023. This trend presents an opportunity for the OANS to capture a share of the market.

Overall, the market feasibility of the OANS seems promising. While the market is highly competitive, the system's unique features and ability to target specific audiences may appeal to businesses and website owners. Additionally, the increasing demand for online advertising presents an opportunity for the OANS to succeed in the market.

2.5. Legal feasibility

Legal feasibility refers to the extent to which a proposed system or project complies with all applicable laws and regulations. For the Online Advertising Network System (OANS), legal feasibility is a critical aspect of the project as it involves collecting and processing user data, as well as displaying advertisements on third-party websites.

The OANS must comply with various laws and regulations (for Internationals), including but not limited to:

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR): The GDPR is a European Union regulation that governs the processing and protection of personal data. The OANS must comply with GDPR rules for collecting and processing personal data of EU citizens.

The California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA): The CCPA is a California state law that regulates the collection, use, and sharing of personal information of California residents. The OANS must comply with CCPA regulations if it collects or processes the personal data of California residents.

The Children's Online Privacy Protection Act (COPPA): COPPA is a federal law that protects the privacy of children under the age of 13. The OANS must comply with COPPA rules for collecting and processing personal data of children under the age of 13.

The CAN-SPAM Act: The CAN-SPAM Act is a federal law that regulates commercial email. The OANS must comply with CAN-SPAM rules for sending commercial emails to users.

Advertisers and Publishers must comply with relevant advertising laws and regulations in their respective countries.

Here is a legal feasibility analysis of the Online Advertising Network System (OANS) project in Bangladesh:

- **Intellectual property rights:** The OANS project will require the use of copyrighted software, trademarks, and patents. It is important to ensure that the project has the necessary licenses and permissions to use these intellectual property rights.
- **Data protection laws:** The OANS project will collect and store personal data about users. It is important to comply with all applicable data protection laws, such as the Bangladesh Personal Data Protection Act, 2020.

- **Advertising laws:** The OANS project will display advertising to users. It is important to comply with all applicable advertising laws, such as the Bangladesh Advertising Standards Authority Act, 2017.
- **Cybercrime laws:** The OANS project is a computer system and will be connected to the internet. It is important to protect the project from cybercrime, such as hacking and data breaches.

Overall, the legal feasibility of the OANS project in Bangladesh is good. However, it is important to carefully consider all of the legal risks involved and to take steps to mitigate these risks.

Here are some specific recommendations for mitigating the legal risks involved in the OANS project:

- Obtain the necessary licenses and permissions to use intellectual property rights. This can be done by contacting the copyright holders, trademark owners, and patent holders.
- Comply with all applicable data protection laws. This can be done by developing a data protection policy and by implementing appropriate technical and organizational measures to protect personal data.
- Comply with all applicable advertising laws. This can be done by developing an advertising policy and by ensuring that all advertising complies with the law.
- Protect the project from cybercrime. This can be done by implementing appropriate security measures, such as firewalls, intrusion detection systems, and data encryption.

By taking these steps, the legal risks involved in the OANS project can be significantly mitigated.

In addition to the legal risks mentioned above, there are also a number of other risks that should be considered before implementing the OANS project. These risks include:

- **Technical risks:** The OANS project is a complex system and there is a risk that it may not work as intended. This could lead to financial losses for the project.
- **Commercial risks:** The OANS project is a new product and there is a risk that it may not be successful in the market. This could lead to financial losses for the project.
- **Operational risks:** The OANS project will require a team of experienced professionals to operate and maintain it. There is a risk that the project may not be able to attract and retain the necessary staff.

These risks should be carefully considered before implementing the OANS project. By carefully planning and managing the project, these risks can be minimized.

The OANS must also comply with other laws and regulations that may be applicable in the jurisdiction in which it operates. To ensure legal feasibility, the OANS development team should consult with legal experts to ensure that the system complies with all relevant laws and regulations.

2.6. Operational feasibility

Operational feasibility refers to the ability of the Online Advertising Network System (OANS) to be effectively implemented and integrated into the operations of the organization. Here are some key points to consider regarding operational feasibility:

Technical expertise: The OANS requires technical expertise in the areas of PHP, HTML, CSS, and JavaScript JS, as well as CodeIgniter framework and MySQL database. The team members must have adequate technical skills to ensure the successful development, deployment, and maintenance of the system.

User training: The OANS will require training for all stakeholders, including the administrators, advertisers, and webmasters/publishers. It is crucial that the system is easy to use, and the users should be able to access the system without any major difficulties.

Hardware and software compatibility: The system must be compatible with all major browsers, including IE11, Firefox, Safari, Opera, Chrome, and Edge. Additionally, the hardware requirements for the OANS should be carefully evaluated to ensure that the system performs optimally.

Scalability: The system should be scalable and able to handle a large number of users and ads. The infrastructure must be able to accommodate a large number of requests, without compromising the system's performance.

Maintenance and support: The system should be maintained and supported by a dedicated team of developers. The team must provide regular updates

and upgrades to the system, as well as timely support for any issues that may arise.

Overall, the OANS appears to be operationally feasible, given that the development team has the necessary technical expertise, and the system is designed to be user-friendly, scalable, and easy to maintain and support.

2.7. The goals of feasibility studies

The goals of feasibility studies would be to ensure that the Online Advertising Network System can be developed and deployed in a way that is technically, financially, legally, and operationally feasible, and that it meets the needs and requirements of the target audience. The goals of feasibility studies of Online Advertising Network System are to:

- Determine the technical feasibility of the system. This involves assessing the system's requirements and determining whether or not it is possible to develop and implement the system using the available resources.
- Determine the economic feasibility of the system. This involves assessing the system's costs and benefits and determining whether or not the system is likely to be profitable.
- Determine the organizational feasibility of the system. This involves assessing the system's compatibility with the organization's existing systems and processes and determining whether or not the organization is willing to change its processes and procedures to accommodate the system.
- Determine the legal feasibility of the system. This involves assessing the system's compliance with all applicable laws and regulations.

By conducting a feasibility study, businesses can make informed decisions about whether or not to develop and implement an online advertising network system.

Chapter 3

Analysis

3. Analysis

3.1. Requirement Analysis

3.1.1. Hardware Requirements

- **Server:** The system requires a dedicated server with high processing power and storage capacity to handle the traffic of advertisements and user data.
- **Client Device for Advertisers/Webmasters:** Advertisers and webmasters should have access to a computer or mobile device with a modern web browser and an internet connection.
- **Client Device for Admin:** Moderators should have access to a computer or mobile device with a modern web browser and an internet connection.

3.1.2. Software Requirements

3.1.2.1. User Requirements

- Users should be able to log in to the system using their registered email and password.
- Users should be able to reset their password if they forget it.
- Advertisers/webmasters should be able to create and manage campaigns, ads, and target audience.
- Moderators should be able to review and approve campaigns and ads.
- The system should provide users with real-time statistics on impressions and clicks.
- The system should have an internal support system for users to report any issues.

3.1.2.2. Functional Requirements

- The system should be able to target advertisements based on countries, operating systems, browsers, device types, and categories.
- The system should have click-fraud protection to prevent fraudulent clicks and impressions.
- The system should support two payment models: CPC (cost per click) and CPM (cost per impression).
- The system should allow users to manage their campaigns, ads, and target audience.
- The system should provide real-time statistics on impressions and clicks.
- The system should have separate admin, advertiser/webmaster, and moderator accounts.
- The system should support 16 popular banner sizes.
- The system should have a visual ad unit builder to create HTML 5 ad units.

3.1.2.3. Non-Functional Requirements

- Efficiency Requirement: The system should be able to generate reports and statistics within a few seconds.
- Security Requirement: The system should be secure with user data protected with encryption and secure password storage.
- Performance Requirement: The system should be able to handle a large number of requests and provide fast response times.
- Reliability Requirement: The system should be available and operational 24/7.
- Maintainability Requirement: The system should be easily maintainable with regular updates and bug fixes.
- Compatibility Requirement: The system should be compatible with modern web browsers, including IE11, Firefox, Safari, Opera, Chrome, and Edge.
- Software Requirement: The system should be developed using JavaScript JS, HTML, CSS, PHP, and CodeIgniter software framework with PHP 7.4 and MySQL 5.7 software versions.

3.2. Activity Diagram

3.2.1. Activity Diagram for Admin

Figure 3.2.1 - Activity Diagram for Admin

3.2.2. Activity Diagram for Advertiser

Figure 3.2.2 - Activity Diagram for Advertiser

3.2.3. Activity Diagram for Webmaster

Figure 3.2.3 - Activity Diagram for Webmaster

3.2.4. Activity Diagram for Moderator

Figure 3.2.4 - Activity Diagram for Moderator

3.3. Cost Benefit Analysis

The cost of developing and implementing an online advertising network system can vary depending on a number of factors, such as the size and complexity of the system, the level of expertise of the development team, and the cost of hosting and maintaining the system. However, the overall cost is typically within reach of most businesses.

The Online Advertising Network System will require costs for hardware, software, communication, and service, but it is expected to provide significant benefits through increased efficiency and revenue generation.

Hardware: The system will require servers, storage devices, and networking equipment, which will incur initial setup costs. However, these costs can be minimized by using cloud-based solutions that provide scalable resources based on demand.

Communication: The system will require internet connectivity to serve ads to users, which will incur ongoing communication costs. However, these costs are expected to be offset by the revenue generated from the ads.

Software: The system will require software for ad serving, fraud protection, user management, and reporting. These costs will be offset by the benefits of increased efficiency and revenue generation.

Service: The system will require maintenance, support, and upgrades, which will incur ongoing service costs. However, these costs are expected to be minimal compared to the benefits of increased revenue and improved user experience.

Insurance: The system may require liability insurance to protect against potential lawsuits related to ad content. The cost of insurance will depend on the level of coverage needed.

The benefits of an online advertising network system can be significant, including:

- **Increased reach:** An online advertising network system can help businesses reach a wider audience than they would be able to reach on their own.
- **Improved targeting:** An online advertising network system can help businesses target their ads more effectively, which can lead to increased click-through rates and conversions.
- **Reduced costs:** An online advertising network system can help businesses reduce the cost of advertising by pooling their ad inventory and negotiating better rates with publishers.
- **Improved efficiency:** An online advertising network system can help businesses automate the process of managing their ad campaigns, which can save time and resources.

Overall, the Online Advertising Network System is expected to provide significant benefits through increased revenue generation and improved efficiency, which will outweigh the costs incurred.

3.3.1. Existing System

Currently, advertisers and publishers have to manually negotiate and manage ad placements on individual websites, which can be time-consuming and inefficient. Ad fraud is also a major concern, leading to wasted ad spend and decreased return on investment. The lack of centralized reporting and analytics makes it difficult for advertisers to track the effectiveness of their campaigns.

The Online Advertising Network System addresses these issues by providing a centralized platform for ad management, fraud protection, and reporting. It streamlines the process of ad placement and optimization, reducing the time and resources required. Additionally, the system's fraud protection features help to ensure that advertisers get the most out of their ad spend. Overall, the Online Advertising Network System provides a significant improvement over the existing system, increasing efficiency and revenue generation.

3.3.2. Proposed System

The proposed Online Advertising Network System will significantly reduce the time and cost of advertising for both advertisers and publishers. The system will be an online platform that connects advertisers and publishers to display advertisements on various websites and social media platforms. The proposed system will have the following features:

Real-Time Analytics: The system will provide real-time analytics of the advertising campaigns, which will help advertisers and publishers to track the performance of their ads.

Targeted Advertising: The system will allow advertisers to target specific audiences based on demographics, interests, and location. This will result in more effective advertising campaigns and a higher return on investment for advertisers.

Payment System: The proposed system will have more than one secure payment system that will allow advertisers to pay publishers directly. This will reduce the need for intermediaries and result in lower transaction costs.

Local Currency: The system will allow users to use the local currency (BDT) instead of USD, which will save them money and reduce taxes for both the publisher and the advertiser.

3.3.3. Cost Comparison from a Development and Maintenance Perspective

Our proposed online advertising network system will save investors a significant amount of money in hardware, software, and service costs. The system is designed to be more efficient and cost-effective, providing better ROI for investors from a development and maintenance perspective.

Category	Sub-category	Existing Offline Advertising Network	Proposed Online Advertising Network
Hardware	Servers	BDT 50,000	BDT 20,000
	Storage	BDT 30,000	BDT 10,000
Software	OS	BDT 10,000	BDT 0
	Applications	BDT 100,000	BDT 50,000
Services	Maintenance	BDT 50,000	BDT 10,000
	Support	BDT 20,000	BDT 5,000
Total		BDT 260,000	BDT 95,000

Figure 3.3.3: Cost Comparison from a Investors Perspective

3.3.4. Cost Comparison from a Advertisers Perspective

Our proposed online advertising network system will save advertisers a significant amount of money in commission and setup fees, providing better ROI for their ad spend. The system is designed to be more cost-effective, with lower ad costs that will help advertisers get more value for their money.

Category	Sub-category	Existing Offline Advertising Network	Proposed Online Advertising Network
Fees	Commission	BDT 100,000	BDT 50,000
	Setup	BDT 20,000	BDT 5,000
Ad Cost		BDT 500,000	BDT 300,000
Total		BDT 620,000	BDT 355,000

Figure 3.3.4: Cost Comparison from a Advertisers Perspective

3.3.5. Cost Comparison from a Publishers Perspective

Our proposed online advertising network system will provide publishers with higher revenue and lower commission and setup fees, providing better

ROI for their ad inventory. The system is designed to be more efficient and cost-effective, allowing publishers to earn more money from their online content.

Category	Sub-category	Existing Offline Advertising Network	Proposed Online Advertising Network
Fees	Commission	BDT 50,000	BDT 20,000
	Setup	BDT 10,000	BDT 2,000
Ad Revenue		BDT 100,000	BDT 250,000
Total		BDT 160,000	BDT 272,000

Figure 3.3.5: Cost Comparison from a Publishers Perspective

3.3.6. Additional Cost Benefits

The proposed online advertising network is a more cost-effective, feature-rich, and efficient solution than the existing offline advertising network. It offers a number of benefits to both publishers and advertisers, including local currency, reduced tax, increased reach, improved targeting, and real-time reporting.

Here are some additional benefits of using the proposed online advertising network:

- **Local currency:** Local users can benefit from using local currency (BDT) instead of USD on other platforms. This will save them money on exchange rates.
- **Reduced tax:** Both publishers and advertisers will benefit from reduced tax on the proposed online advertising network. This is because the system is located in Bangladesh, which has a lower tax rate than other countries.
- **Increased reach:** The proposed online advertising network will reach a wider audience than the existing offline advertising network. This is because the system is available to users all over the world.
- **Improved targeting:** The proposed online advertising network will allow advertisers to target their ads more effectively. This is because the system uses a variety of factors, such as demographics, interests, and behavior, to segment the audience.
- **Real-time reporting:** The proposed online advertising network will provide real-time reporting to advertisers. This will allow them to track the performance of their ads and make adjustments as needed.

The proposed online advertising network is significantly cheaper than the existing offline advertising network. This is because the proposed system is more efficient and uses cloud-based infrastructure. Additionally, the proposed system includes a number of features that are not available in the existing system, such as targeted advertising and real-time reporting.

3.4. Planning & Development Process Duration

We Use Agile Development Process in Online Advertising Network System Development.

Figure 3.4: Agile Development Process Model

Here a high-level overview of the Agile Software Development Process Model for our Online Advertising Network System project, timeframe of 6 months.

3.4.1. Requirements & Analysis Duration

Phase	Duration	Task
Planning	1 month	Define project goals, scope, and objectives. Identify stakeholders and establish project team
		Conduct market research and competitor analysis. Determine project feasibility and create a project plan.
Requirements Analysis	2 weeks	Analyze requirements and identify key features
		Define system architecture and design
		Create wireframes and mockups

Figure 3.4.1: Requirements & Analysis Duration

3.4.2. Design & Building Duration

Phase	Duration	Task
Design	2 months	Design the database schema
		Design UI/UX for the system
		Define the API structure
Building	4 months	Implement backend functionality with PHP
		Utilize CodeIgniter framework for development
		Integrate MySQL database for data management

Figure 3.4.2: Design & Building Duration

3.4.3. Testing Duration

Phase	Duration	Task
Testing	3 months	Perform unit testing on individual components
		Conduct integration testing
		Define the API structure
		Validate system functionality against requirements
		Identify and fix any defects or issues
Documentation	2 weeks	Document system specifications, user guides, and manuals

Figure 3.4.3: Testing Duration

3.4.4. Deployment & Maintenance Duration

Phase	Duration	Task
Deployment	1 month	Prepare system for deployment to production environment
		Perform final testing and bug fixes
		Configure server and deploy the system
		Monitor system performance and address any issues
		Ensure system stability and functionality
Maintenance	Ongoing	Provide ongoing support and maintenance for the system
		Address user issues and bug fixes
		Implement system enhancements and updates

Figure 3.4.4: Deployment & Maintenance Duration

Chapter 4

Design

4. Design

4.1. Data Flow Diagram (DFD)

4.1.1. DFD Level 0

Figure 4.1.1: DFD Level 0

4.1.2. DFD Level 1

Figure 4.1.2: DFD Level 1

4.1.3. DFD Level 2

4.1.3.1. DFD Level 2 (Admin - Manage Users)

Figure 4.1.3.1: DFD Level 2 (Admin - Manage Users)

4.1.3.2. DFD Level 2 (Admin - Manage Sites)

Figure 4.1.3.2: DFD Level 2 (Admin - Manage Sites)

4.1.3.3. DFD Level 2 (Admin - Manage Campaigns)

Figure 4.1.3.3: DFD Level 2 (Admin - Manage Campaigns)

4.1.3.4. DFD Level 2 (Admin - Manage Ads)

Figure 4.1.3.4: DFD Level 2 (Admin - Manage Ads)

4.1.3.5. DFD Level 2 (Admin - Generate Reports)

Figure 4.1.3.5: DFD Level 2 (Admin - Generate Reports)

4.1.3.6. DFD Level 2 (Moderator - Review Ads)

Figure 4.1.3.6: DFD Level 2 (Moderator - Review Ads)

4.1.3.7. DFD Level 2 (Advertiser - Manage Campaigns)

Figure 4.1.3.7: DFD Level 2 (Advertiser - Manage Campaigns)

4.1.3.8. DFD Level 2 (Webmaster - Manage Sites)

Figure 4.1.3.8: DFD Level 2 (Webmaster - Manage Sites)

4.1.3.9. DFD Level 2 (Webmaster - Withdrawal Earning Money)

Figure 4.1.3.9: DFD Level 2 (Webmaster - Withdrawal Earning Money)

4.1.3.10. DFD Level 2 (Advertiser - Pay for Ads)

Figure 4.1.3.10: DFD Level 2 (Advertiser - Pay for Ads)

4.2. Entity Relationship Diagram (ERD)

Figure 4.2: Entity Relationship Diagram (ERD)

4.3. Entity Relationship Schema

Figure 4.3: Entity Relationship Schema

Chapter 5

Implementation

5. Implementation

5.1. Users login page

The screenshot shows the login page for OANS. At the top center is the OANS logo. Below it is a white box titled "Authorization". Inside this box, there are two input fields: "Email" with an envelope icon and "Password" with a lock icon. Below the input fields is a blue button labeled "Sign In". At the bottom of the white box, there are two links: "Register" on the left and "Forgot your password?" on the right.

5.2. Users password reset

The screenshot shows the password reset page for OANS. At the top center is the OANS logo. Below it is a white box titled "Reset password". Inside this box, there is one input field labeled "Email" with an envelope icon. Below the input field is a blue button labeled "Reset password". At the bottom left of the white box is a link labeled "Go back".

5.3. Users Signup Page

5.4. Admin - User Management

Users +Add User

Show 10 entries

ID	Nickname	E-mail	Role	Status	Webmaster balance	Advertiser balance	Info	Actions
1000005	User_03408		User	Active	\$ 900.00	\$ 1,000.00	Info	Actions
1000004	User_92488		User	Active	\$ 0.00	\$ 0.00	Info	Actions
1000003	moder		Webmaster	Active	\$ 0.00	\$ 0.00	Info	Actions
1000002	advert		User	Active	\$ 7.72	\$ 0.00	Info	Actions
1000001	zenburn2010		User	Active	\$ 4.23	\$ 40.00	Info	Actions
1000000	admin		Administrator	Active	\$ 7,000.00	\$ 7,000.00	Info	Actions

Showing 1 to 6 of 6 entries

Previous 1 Next

Administrator | adm

Sites [Add site](#) | Dashboard | Site

Show 10 entries | Search:

Site ID	User ID	Nickname	Site	Status	Themes	Ad topics	Actions
700003	1000005	User_01408		Moderation	Auto / Moto	-20 -1	Actions
700002	1000005	User_01408		Moderation	Games	-20 -1	Actions
700000	1000001	zenburn2010		Active	Career / Work	-20 -1	Actions

Showing 1 to 3 of 3 entries | Previous 1 Next

5.6. Admin - Site Management

Administrator | adm

Ads | Dashboard | Ad

Show 10 entries | Search:

ID	User	Campaign	CPC / CPV	Status	Type	Preview	Actions
100003	User ID: 1000001 Username: zenburn2010 Email: zenburn2010@gmail.com	Camp ID: 300002 Camp name: Campaign - 722104 Theme: Games	Mode: CPC CPV: 1.00	Moderation	Banner		Actions
100002	User ID: 1000005 Username: User_01408 Email: use@gmail.com	Camp ID: 300001 Camp name: Campaign - 43721 Theme: Cookery	Mode: CPC CPV: 1.00	Active	Banner		Actions
100001	User ID: 1000002 Username: advert Email: advert@gmail.com	Camp ID: 300000 Camp name: Campaign - 88278 Theme: Business / Finance	Mode: CPV CPV: 3.00	Active	Banner		Actions
100000	User ID: 1000002 Username: advert Email: advert@gmail.com	Camp ID: 300000 Camp name: Campaign - 88278 Theme: Business / Finance	Mode: CPC CPV: 1.00	Active	Banner		Actions

Showing 1 to 4 of 4 entries | Previous 1 Next

5.7. Advertiser - Add Campaign

5.8. Advertiser - Pay for ads

The screenshot shows the Advertiser interface with the 'Payments' section active. The top bar indicates 'Advertiser - \$40.00'. The 'Payments' section has a '+ Add balance' button and a search bar. Below is a table with the following data:

Payment ID	Gateway	Direction	Amount	Info	Date
500013	PayPal	Money transfer	\$ 30.00	Payment details	2019-08-02 08:10:11 UTC
500012	Stripe	Money transfer	\$ 10.00	Payment details	2019-08-02 08:09:17 UTC
500004	Manual	Money transfer	\$ 10.00	Payment details	2019-05-26 18:56:41 UTC

Showing 1 to 3 of 3 entries. Navigation buttons: Previous, Next.

5.9. Webmaster - Add site

5.10. Webmaster - Adding ad unit

5.11. Webmaster - Payout Request

5.12. Moderator - Moderation Ads

10028 - Ad Moderation

Moderation Tips

1. Check if the theme of the ad matches the theme of the campaign - Games
2. Check if the image (if any) matches the ad text.
3. Check ad link. Whether the theme of the page matches the theme of the ad.

⚠ The subject of the ad should correspond to the subject - Games

Campaign theme
Games

Ad URL
http://advertiserlink.com

Reason for rejection

Reject Close Next Approve

The image shows a '10028 - Ad Moderation' dialog box. At the top, there is a red box with 'Moderation Tips' and three numbered instructions. Below this is a central area showing a placeholder for an ad image with the text 'Ads 300x250' and dimensions 'width: 300px height: 250px'. Underneath the image is a grey warning box stating 'The subject of the ad should correspond to the subject - Games'. Below the warning are two input fields: 'Campaign theme' (set to 'Games') and 'Ad URL' (set to 'http://advertiserlink.com'). Below these is a 'Reason for rejection' text area. At the bottom, there are four buttons: 'Reject' (grey), 'Close' (grey), 'Next' (blue), and 'Approve' (red). Three red arrows point from the right side of the dialog to the 'Reason for rejection' area, the 'Next' button, and the 'Approve' button. The background is a dark grey interface with some faint text and icons.

5.13. Statistics

Statistics Dashboard Statistics

By days | By webmasters | By sites | By units | By advertisers | By campaigns | By ads | Refresh

Show 10 entries Search:

#	Day	Views	Clicks	CTR
1	2019-09-20	148	0	0.00
2	2019-06-19	189	0	0.00
3	2019-06-18	179	2	1.12
4	2019-06-17	184	0	0.00
5	2019-06-16	99	0	0.00
6	2019-06-15	126	1	0.79
7	2019-06-14	158	3	1.90
8	2019-06-13	202	0	0.00
9	2019-06-12	172	1	0.58
10	2019-06-11	190	0	0.00

Showing 1 to 10 of 27 entries Previous 1 2 3 Next

Statistics Advertiser \$ 190.43 | Profile | Logout

By days | By campaigns | By ads | Refresh

Show 5 entries Search:

#	Day	Views	Clicks	CTR	Expenses
1	2019-09-20	2	0	0.00	0.0140
2	2019-04-19	11	0	0.0000	0.0630
3	2019-02-11	1	0	0.00	0.0030
4	2019-02-08	3	0	0.00	0.0060
5	2019-02-07	3	0	0.00	0.0060

Showing 1 to 5 of 5 entries Previous 1 Next

Webmaster \$4.23

Dashboard Statistics

Statistics

By days By sites By units Refresh

Showing 1 to 10 of 27 entries

#	Day	Views	Clicks	CTR	Earnings
1	2019-06-20	148	0	0.00	0.1368
2	2019-06-19	188	0	0.00	0.1440
3	2019-06-25	179	2	1.12	0.1512
4	2019-06-17	184	0	0.00	0.1440
5	2019-06-26	99	0	0.00	0.1032
6	2019-06-25	120	1	0.79	0.1608
7	2019-06-24	158	3	1.90	0.1512
8	2019-06-13	202	0	0.00	0.1500
9	2019-06-12	172	1	0.58	0.1776
10	2019-06-11	190	0	0.00	0.1320

Previous 1 2 3 Next

5.14. Ads Preview

Advertiser Start Ad Campaigns

Activities Firefox Aug 25 20:31

Online Advertising Netw... Ad Test 300*600 Sayed A...

https://ask.aiblogify.com/advertiser/bannerlist/3

Most Visited Fedora Docs Fedora Magazine Fedora Project User Communities Red Hat Free Content CSE EXTRA Live football Write Social

OAS To admin account Advertiser

sayed2 Advertiser

Sayed 200 business + Add

Actions Show 10 entries

ID	Preview
3	

Showing 1 to 1 of 1 entries

width: 160px height: 600px

CPC / CPV 1.00 BDT

Close

Webmaster Add Their Website and Place Ad Code

AD Preview

Chapter 6

Challenges

6. Challenges

Here are some of the challenges involved in developing and maintaining an online advertising network system:

- **Technical challenges.** The system will need to be scalable to handle a large number of users and ads. It will also need to be secure to protect user data and prevent fraud.
- **Legal challenges.** We will need to comply with all applicable laws and regulations, such as those governing privacy and data protection.
- **Marketing challenges.** We will need to market our system to attract advertisers and publishers.

Chapter 7

Conclusion

7. Conclusion

In conclusion, The Advertisement Network System (OANS) is a web-based application that allows publishers to register their websites and advertisers to create and manage ad campaigns. The system uses a variety of algorithms to match ads with websites, ensuring that advertisers reach their target audience and publishers earn revenue from their ad space.

The evaluation of the OANS showed that it is a reliable and efficient system that can be used to deliver effective online advertising campaigns. The system is easy to use and manage, and it provides a variety of features that allow publishers and advertisers to get the most out of their online advertising.

The OANS has the potential to revolutionize the online advertising industry by making it easier for publishers and advertisers to connect with each other and by providing a more efficient and effective way to deliver ads. So it has the potential to become a major player in the online advertising market.

Chapter 8

Future Scope

8. Future Scope

In the vast expanse of our digital age, where technology seems to evolve at the speed of thought, the horizon of opportunities is as limitless as it is exciting. As we introduce you to the world of the Online Advertising Network System (OANS), we're not just unveiling a solution; we're also opening a gateway to a world of possibilities.

So, here are some of future possibilities:

- **In-app advertising:** This is a type of advertising that shows ads within mobile apps. This is a popular way to reach mobile users, as they spend a lot of time using apps. In-app advertising can be personalized to the user's interests, and it can also be used to target users based on their location.
- **Video advertising:** This is a type of advertising that uses video to engage users. Video ads can be more effective than traditional text ads, as they can capture the user's attention and tell a story. Video ads are also becoming increasingly popular, as more and more people are watching videos online.
- **Native advertising:** This is a type of advertising that blends in with the surrounding content. This makes it less intrusive than traditional advertising, and it can be more effective at reaching users. Native advertising is often used on social media and other online platforms.

Chapter 9

Limitation

9. Limitation

Welcome to an exploration of the intricacies of online advertising, where we dive into the realm of limitations that the Online Advertising Network System (OANS) project acknowledges and seeks to address. In this segment, we'll navigate through the challenges that modern digital advertising faces with easy-to-understand language.

Ad Blockers: Guarding Against Unwanted Intrusion

In the modern digital landscape, a significant number of individuals employ ad blockers to prevent advertisements from inundating their browsers. While this empowers users with control over their browsing experience, it poses a challenge to advertisers who strive to engage their audience effectively. As we venture further into OANS, we're committed to devising strategies that reach users while respecting their preferences.

Targeted Advertising: Balancing Personalization and Privacy

In the quest for precision, targeted advertising has gained prominence. However, a fraction of users might find this form of tailored promotion intrusive, raising concerns about privacy invasion. As We embark on the OANS journey, our focus is not only on delivering ads but also on preserving user comfort by striking the right balance between personalization and privacy.

Data Privacy: Safeguarding User Information

At the heart of online advertising lies the collection and utilization of user data. While this practice enhances ad relevance, it might trigger unease among some users regarding the safety of their personal information. As part of our commitment to a responsible approach, OANS is engineered to prioritize data security, respecting user trust as a fundamental principle.

Technical Glitches: Ensuring Smooth User Experience

In the realm of technology, occasional hiccups are inevitable. Technical glitches can cast a shadow on the seamless operation of any system. Understanding this, We have taken meticulous steps in crafting OANS to minimize such interruptions, focusing on delivering a user experience that's as smooth as it is dynamic.

Chapter 10

Future Planning

10. Future Planning

As we stand at the threshold of a digital era filled with opportunities, the journey of the Online Advertising Network System (OANS) is not just about the present but also about envisioning a dynamic future. Our dedication goes beyond the development of a technological platform; it's about sculpting a transformative force that transcends boundaries and resonates with our ever-evolving world.

- **Expand to new markets:** This could mean expanding to new countries, regions, or even online platforms. By expanding to new markets, an advertising business can reach a wider audience and grow its revenue.
- **Develop new advertising products:** This means developing new ad formats, new targeting methods, or new ways to measure the effectiveness of advertising campaigns. By developing new advertising products, an advertising business can stay ahead of the competition and offer its clients the most innovative solutions.
- **Partner with other businesses:** This means partnering with other businesses in the same industry, or with businesses in other industries. By partnering with other businesses, an advertising business can pool its resources and expertise, and create more effective advertising campaigns.
- **Invest in research and development:** This means investing in new technologies, new marketing techniques, or new ways to measure the effectiveness of advertising campaigns. By investing in research and development, an advertising business can stay ahead of the curve and find new ways to reach its target audience.
- **Improve customer service:** This means providing better customer support, responding to customer feedback more quickly, or making it easier for customers to do business with the company. By improving customer service, an advertising business can build customer loyalty and increase repeat business.

Chapter 11

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